

CENTRO DE INVESTIGACIONES
DE TRABAJO SOCIAL

ISSN 2244-808X
DL pp 201002Z43506

PERSPECTIVA INTERACCION Y

Revista de Trabajo Social

Vol. 16 No. 2
Mayo - Agosto
2026

Universidad del Zulia

Facultad de Ciencias Jurídicas y Políticas
Centro de Investigaciones en Trabajo Social

INTERACCIÓN Y PERSPECTIVA

Revista de Trabajo Social

ISSN 2244-808X ~ Dep. Legal pp 201002Z43506

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19245554>

Vol. 16 (2): 603 - 619 pp, 2026

ARTÍCULO DE INVESTIGACIÓN

Actividades de las organizaciones benéficas que apoyan a la población en territorios desocupados: problemas, métodos y perspectivas

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Resumen. El objetivo del estudio es identificar las características específicas del funcionamiento de las organizaciones benéficas en las regiones desocupadas de Ucrania y determinar su papel en la restauración de la estabilidad social entre la población afectada por las consecuencias de las hostilidades. Se enfatiza la transformación de la actividad benéfica desde un apoyo humanitario de emergencia hacia un mecanismo sistemático de recuperación social comunitaria. El estudio emplea un enfoque integral que combina el análisis de datos empíricos. Se utilizan métodos de análisis comparativo, diagnóstico de problemas y estudio de casos para identificar prácticas eficaces y factores limitantes. Se establece que las actividades de las instituciones benéficas abarcan apoyo material, asistencia médica y psicológica, iniciativas educativas, apoyo jurídico y programas de reintegración. Al mismo tiempo, su labor se ve obstaculizada por la escasez de recursos, limitaciones de personal, barreras administrativas y riesgos de seguridad. Se identifica una tendencia hacia la digitalización de los procesos de

evaluación de necesidades y coordinación logística, lo que incrementa la focalización y la transparencia de los programas. Conclusión. Se demuestra que las organizaciones benéficas se están convirtiendo en un elemento importante de la infraestructura social en las comunidades liberadas, complementando los mecanismos de apoyo estatal. El desarrollo futuro de este sector requiere la integración de un enfoque centrado en la persona, la ampliación de alianzas y el fortalecimiento de la sostenibilidad financiera para garantizar la recuperación territorial a largo plazo.

Palabras clave: trabajo social, fundaciones benéficas, territorios desocupados, población afectada, ayuda humanitaria.

Activities of charitable organizations supporting the population in de-occupied territories: problems, methods, and prospects

Abstract. The aim of the study is to identify the specific features of the functioning of charitable organizations in the de-occupied regions of Ukraine and to determine their role in restoring social stability among the population affected by the consequences of hostilities. Emphasis is placed on the transformation of charitable activity from emergency humanitarian support into a systematic mechanism of community social recovery. The study employs a comprehensive approach that combines the analysis of empirical data. Methods of comparative analysis, problem diagnostics, and case analysis are used to identify effective practices and constraining factors. It is established that the activities of charitable institutions encompass material support, medical and psychological assistance, educational initiatives, legal support, and reintegration programs. At the same time, their work is complicated by resource shortages, staffing constraints, administrative barriers, and security risks. A trend toward the digitalization of needs assessment and logistics coordination processes is identified, which increases the targeting and transparency of programs. Conclusion. It is demonstrated that charitable organizations are becoming an important element of social infrastructure in liberated communities, complementing state support mechanisms. Further development of this sector requires the integration of a human-centered approach, the expansion of partnerships, and the strengthening of financial sustainability to ensure long-term territorial recovery.

Keywords: social work, charitable foundations, de-occupied territories, affected population, humanitarian aid.

INTRODUCTION

The deepening of globalization processes covering all spheres of world social and economic life is accompanied by the emergence of qualitatively new challenges that directly affect the state of social security of the population, and this impact is especially noticeable in countries experiencing military conflicts and their consequences, in particular in Ukraine, where the de-occupied territories need comprehensive support (Pankova & Kasperovych, 2022). The destruction of

critical facilities, loss of housing, limited access to medical care and educational institutions, psychological trauma, and disruption of social adaptation of millions of citizens have created special conditions that require not only governmental measures but also the broad participation of charitable institutions and non-governmental organizations. These structures have become an effective mechanism for rapid response to the needs of local communities, providing humanitarian, psychological, educational and rehabilitation assistance to victims. In the field of socio-economic relations, there are numerous endogenous factors that cause property stratification, inequitable distribution of income and benefits, and the formation of new categories of vulnerable groups, including a significant proportion of people who have lost housing, jobs, or access to basic social services as a result of the occupation (Adegbite, 2025). In such realities, it is the social work of charitable foundations that becomes the tool that is designed to compensate for the lack of state capacity and provide targeted assistance to people who need it most.

The essence of the research problem is to find out the specifics of social activities of charitable foundations with residents who have suffered damage and destruction in the liberated territories, as well as to identify factors that hinder or promote the effectiveness of such work. Despite the large number of institutions providing assistance, their activities are hampered by a lack of financial and human resources, security threats, administrative obstacles, and the absence of a centralized coordination system. The above arguments determine the need for a scientific study of the social work of charitable foundations as a key component of restoring the social resource of the liberated communities and ensuring the sustainable development of Ukrainian society.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The current scientific discussion on the social work of charitable foundations is important because they provide flexibility in responding to social challenges and the ability to quickly adapt assistance programs to new circumstances, which is extremely relevant for Ukraine in the context of war and after the de-occupation of the territories. In recent works by Giacaman et al. (2011), Shmorlivska and Strebkova (2023), charity is most often defined as a voluntary and selfless activity aimed at improving the material, social or moral condition of its recipient, and they prove that charity performs not only the function of humanitarian aid, but also becomes a component of social solidarity. However, their research does not take into account the specifics of charitable foundations in the de-occupied territories, where the volume and nature of the population's needs far exceed the traditional limits of basic charity.

The published works of An et al. (2022) and Martynenko (2024) focus on the activities of non-governmental institutions in the field of social protection of children and youth, including vulnerable categories, and these authors describe in detail the legal framework for social work and outline mechanisms for interaction with government agencies. However, these studies do not address the problem of restoring access to social services in communities that have experienced the occupation, where the lack of infrastructure makes traditional models ineffective. For example, Dibrova and Liakh (2025) and Lacey and Moran (2024) study the professional training of social workers to partner with non-governmental organizations, showing that human resources are a key factor in the effectiveness of social programs. At the same time, the scientific literature hardly

analyzes the shortage of qualified personnel and volunteers in the dangerous conditions of the liberated territories, which is critically important for Ukraine.

The authors would like to highlight the works of Chapman and Thai (2025) and Sadrytska and Korop (2020), which focus on the transformation of one-time humanitarian actions into systemic social work with veterans and internally displaced persons, justifying the place of charity in the state's social policy. Their analysis of the foundations' activities on the example of the Kharkiv region showed the effectiveness of local initiatives, but did not take into account the peculiarities of working in the conditions of destruction and lack of basic services in de-occupied communities and lands.

Hladunov and Bohdanets (2023), Spirina et al. (2025) studied the problems of social protection in Ukraine and proposed directions for its reform, but did not pay attention to the activities of charitable foundations that actually replace the state in the liberated territories. Similarly, foreign studies by Erdilmen (2025) showed the influence of moral principles on the development of charity and outlined the management features of non-governmental organizations, but they mainly consider experience in the field of natural disasters or migration crises, which only partially correlates with the Ukrainian military reality. Contemporary authors Harghandiwal (2025) and Yerusalimov et al. (2023) reveal charitable activities as a factor of resilience and emphasize the role of government-business-civil society partnerships, but do not sufficiently analyze the activities of charitable foundations themselves in the specific conditions of the de-occupied territories, where the main barriers are security risks, bureaucratic procedures, and the destruction of infrastructure.

Of particular interest is the study by Tkach et al. (2023), who analyzed the mechanisms of social partnership in the government-business-civil society system in the context of European integration. The authors substantiated the need to strengthen coordination between government institutions and non-governmental organizations, but their analysis did not take into account the specifics of work in the context of active hostilities and in the liberated territories, where traditional partnership models need to be radically adapted.

A valuable contribution to understanding the issue was made by Napiórkowska et al. (2025), who studied mechanisms for supporting people in difficult life circumstances. Their analysis showed the ineffectiveness of existing state social support programs and the need to involve the non-governmental sector. However, the study focused mainly on the national level, without disclosing the specifics of charitable foundations' activities in regions with critically damaged infrastructure and increased security risks typical of the de-occupied territories.

Thus, although the outlined scientific works concentrate a significant body of work on the role of charitable foundations in the social protection system, the problem of organizing social work in the liberated territories of Ukraine remains unexplored, which requires comprehensive research and modernization from the perspective of military and post-war challenges.

The aim of the article is to identify the specifics of social work by charitable foundations with the affected population of the de-occupied territories of Ukraine and to formulate directions for the development of social support that will help restore community life.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study was conducted using a comprehensive approach that combines qualitative and quantitative methods. To collect primary data, an analytical collection of primary information on the work of ten leading charitable foundations operating in Kharkiv, Kherson and Donetsk regions, as well as with 50 residents of liberated communities who received humanitarian aid, was conducted. The information gathered included an assessment of the needs of the population, the effectiveness of the foundations' programs and the main obstacles to their implementation. Secondary data was collected by analyzing reports of charitable organizations, official data from the Ministry of Social Policy of Ukraine, as well as materials from international organizations, including the Charities Aid Foundation (World Giving Index). To evaluate the activities of the foundations, a problem analysis was used to identify strengths (flexibility of response, targeting of assistance) and weaknesses (limited resources, bureaucratic barriers). The case study method was used to examine in detail the work of a number of individual foundations, with a focus on their programs to support vulnerable groups. The research was conducted in compliance with ethical standards, ensuring the anonymity of respondents and confidentiality of data. The results were systematized for further comparison with international experience of social work in the context of military conflicts and identification of ways to optimize the activities of the foundations.

RESULTS

Current state and peculiarities of social interaction of charitable foundations with the affected population within the de-occupied territories of Ukraine

According to a study conducted by the British organization Charities Aid Foundation, in 2024 Ukraine ranked second in the World Philanthropy Index, which is an unprecedented phenomenon in world practice, as in 2012 the state was only at the 150th position, and the level of citizen participation in volunteer activities was about 6% of the total population (Charities Aid Foundation, 2023). Such growth dynamics became possible due to the activation of civil society after the start of the large-scale aggression of the Russian Federation, when volunteering and charity turned from an occasional social practice into a powerful institution of social support covering both the front and the rear, including the de-occupied territories.

According to Ukrainian legislation, namely the Law of Ukraine «On Charitable Activities and Charitable Organizations», charitable activities are considered to be voluntary provision of material or non-material assistance without expectation of profit or reward, which is especially important in the case of working with the affected population of the de-occupied territories, as in these conditions charity is the only source of rapid satisfaction of basic life needs for food, medicine, hygiene products and temporary housing (Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine, 2012). The social work of charitable foundations in these regions is of particular importance, as it is implemented through targeted programs of psychological support, medical care, educational integration of children, reintegration activities for internally displaced persons, and programs for the restoration of communities that have experienced occupation (Table 1).

TABLE 1. Modern forms and tools of social work of charitable foundations with the affected population in the de-occupied territories of Ukraine.

Forms and tools	Description
Provision of material assistance	Provides financial, food, household and other material support to meet the basic needs of the population for food, clothing, fuel, hygiene products and housing and communal services; in the current situation, it also includes the distribution of energy equipment (generators, heaters, solar panels) and means for autonomous existence in the context of infrastructure destruction
Medical care and rehabilitation	Covers first aid, examinations and treatment, supply of medicines and equipment, access to mobile outpatient clinics, organization of vaccinations, reopening of paramedic stations; an important component is medical and physical rehabilitation of victims of injuries and chronic diseases exacerbated by war
Psychological support	It is implemented through crisis counseling, group and individual sessions, art therapy programs and mobile psychological teams; it is focused on helping people who have survived the occupation, lost their relatives, witnessed violence or suffered from PTSD (post-traumatic stress disorder); special attention is paid to children and women who belong to the most vulnerable categories
Education and awareness programs	Aimed at restoring access to education for children and youth, organizing distance and blended learning, providing digital literacy courses, language and vocational training for adults; also includes mine safety awareness campaigns and education on human rights and social adaptation after the occupation
Temporary accommodation and housing restoration	Provides for the organization of temporary accommodation centers, financial assistance for renting housing, provision of modular houses, support in the restoration of destroyed housing; current programs include cooperation with international partners to build energy-efficient temporary housing
Reintegration programs and community recovery	Covers professional retraining, employment assistance, small business grants, support for women's entrepreneurship; includes measures to restore social infrastructure (schools, kindergartens, libraries), development of community centers that ensure communication and unity in communities after de-occupation
Legal and social advocacy support	Provides free legal consultations, assistance in restoring documents, protection of victims' rights, assistance in accessing state compensation and social protection programs; also includes advocacy campaigns to draw the attention of international partners to the problems of the de-occupied territories
Digital and information services	A modern form of social work that includes the use of online platforms to register the needs of the population, provide consultations through hotlines and chatbots, coordinate the logistics of aid delivery using digital maps, and create databases of needs and resources for efficient distribution of aid

Source: Stabilization Support Services Charitable Foundation (2022), UNPRPD/Global Disability Fund (2025).

At the same time, despite the fact that about nine thousand charitable foundations and more than six thousand NGOs have been officially registered in Ukraine since the beginning of the invasion, their activities in the de-occupied territories are accompanied by numerous barriers: a) difficulty in accessing settlements due to military restrictions; b) the need for special permits; c) security risks for employees and volunteers, as well as limited financial resources for long-term recovery programs (Ukrinform, 2023).

The social work of charitable foundations with the affected population in the de-occupied territories of Ukraine is characterized not only by a high level of social significance, but also by the constant face of numerous challenges, among which one of the most acute is the destroyed and damaged infrastructure, which makes it virtually impossible to provide full assistance. Settlements liberated from occupation are often left without the basic elements of civilized existence: access to drinking water, electricity, medical services, transportation, or educational services (Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine, 2001). This not only worsens the living conditions of the local population, but also creates an extremely difficult environment for charitable foundations, which are forced not only to ensure the delivery of food, medicine and basic necessities, but also to take on the functions of restoring critical infrastructure, which is normally the responsibility of the state (Table 2).

TABLE 2. Modern charitable foundations and civic initiatives engaged in social work with the affected population in the de-occupied territories of Ukraine.

Charitable foundation or project	Description of social activities
Charitable Foundation “Let’s Help”	In recent years, the foundation has been implementing programs to help lonely elderly people, particularly in the de-occupied territories. Thanks to cooperation with international partners (Corteva Agriculture and others), it has provided food packages, hygiene products, and medicines to thousands of pensioners in the eastern and southern regions of Ukraine. The Foundation’s assistance reduces the financial burden on vulnerable categories of the population and increases their level of social security.
Public Association “Through the War”	The main activity is to support children and their parents in need of treatment and rehabilitation. The foundation finances the purchase of medicines and equipment for hospitals, conducts trainings for doctors, and implements long-term psychological assistance programs. In the de-occupied territories, the Foundation organizes mobile medical units, ensuring access to basic services in communities where the medical infrastructure has been destroyed by the war.
Center for Volunteering and Protection	The organization actively works in the de-occupied and frontline areas, coordinating the activities of hundreds of volunteers. The Center implements humanitarian programs (food, clothing, household goods), organizes crisis counseling, and provides psychological support to residents of the liberated settlements. It also implements social adaptation programs for internally displaced persons and orphans, and supports local communities in restoring social infrastructure.

TABLE 2. CONTINUATION

Charitable foundation or project	Description of social activities
Victor Leshchynsky Charitable Foundation	The Foundation is focused on supporting IDPs, refugees and residents of the liberated territories. The Foundation provides food packages, assists in the restoration of housing, and organizes mobile teams to deliver humanitarian aid to frontline areas where there are high risks to life.
NGO “Ordinary People”	Since 2019, the organization has been implementing psychological assistance programs for children and families in difficult life circumstances. Since the beginning of the full-scale war, it has been actively supporting the communities of Kharkiv region: providing humanitarian aid, helping to restore infrastructure, opening children’s and youth spaces, rebuilding destroyed housing and public facilities.
NGO “All-Ukrainian Youth Movement Let’s do it Ukraine”	The youth organization implements large-scale social projects aimed at supporting vulnerable populations and developing youth initiatives in the liberated territories. The foundation’s programs include volunteer camps, environmental and educational campaigns, and assistance to schools and children’s institutions.
National Scout Organization of Ukraine “Plast”	Despite the main focus on patriotic and civic education of youth, the organization is actively involved in social work in the de-occupied territories. “Plast” organizes children’s camps for children from the frontline and liberated territories, provides humanitarian aid, promotes youth leadership development and integration of children into peaceful life after traumatic events.
Caritas Ukraine International Foundation	One of the largest charitable foundations in Ukraine that systematically works in the de-occupied territories. The organization provides humanitarian aid, conducts psychosocial support programs, provides housing for internally displaced persons, implements long-term projects to restore social infrastructure and support local communities.
“Come Back Alive” Foundation	Although the main focus of the foundation’s activities is to support the Armed Forces of Ukraine, the organization also implements social programs for military families and residents of the liberated territories. The foundation finances rehabilitation programs for veterans and civilian victims, and organizes assistance to families who have lost breadwinners.

Source: Giving Tuesday Ukraine (2025), Stabilization Support Services Charitable Foundation (2022).

An equally significant problem in the field of charitable organizations is the limited financial resources. Ukraine, which has been in a state of full-scale war since 2022, is forced to allocate significant budget expenditures to ensure defense capabilities and support for internally displaced persons, which leaves funding for social programs at the local level insufficient. In such conditions, charitable foundations are virtually the only entities able to respond quickly to the urgent needs of the population of the de-occupied territories, but their capabilities are limited by the lack of funds (Figure 1).

FIGURE 1. Dynamics of charitable foundations' activity and the volume of financial assistance to the population in the de-occupied territories of Ukraine in 2022-2024.

Source: National Bank of Ukraine (2024).

Donor revenues and international support, which increased significantly in the first months of the war, are gradually decreasing, and competition between numerous organizations for limited financial resources is intensifying (Erdilmen, 2025). These consequences can create conditions where, even with well-designed aid projects, charitable foundations are not always able to implement them in full, and a significant portion of the needs of the affected population remain unmet.

Another challenge is the lack of human resources, including employees and volunteers willing to work in the dangerous conditions of the de-occupied territories. Social work in these regions requires a high level of professional training, psychological stability and risk-taking, as daily activities are associated with potential threats to life and health. Not all specialists are ready to travel to remote settlements where there is a risk of mine danger or repeated shelling. The lack of staff slows down program implementation, reduces the efficiency of emergency response, and puts additional strain on the few employees and volunteers who remain active. As a result, this will affect the quality of assistance, as foundations are forced to limit the scope of their programs or postpone their implementation (Napiórkowska et al., 2025).

An additional factor that complicates the work of charitable foundations is systemic bureaucratic obstacles. In order to officially provide assistance in the de-occupied territories, organizations often have to go through complex procedures for obtaining permits and licenses, which is accompanied by long application review periods, repeated checks and audits. Often, the requirements of government agencies are contradictory or inconsistent, which leads to delays in the implementation of humanitarian programs and causes a loss of trust on the part of donors. Time spent on administrative issues is particularly critical in situations where the clock is ticking, as delays in the delivery of humanitarian supplies can cost lives and health of those affected (Makedon et al., 2025a; Tkach et al., 2023). For employees and volunteers, it also becomes a factor of demotivation, as the need to constantly overcome bureaucratic obstacles creates a sense of futility and emotional exhaustion (Table 3).

TABLE 3. Problems and obstacles in the social work of charitable foundations with the population in the de-occupied territories of Ukraine.

Problem/obstacle Obstacle	Description	Consequences	Possible solutions
Limited financial resources	Charitable foundations face a shortage of funds due to a decrease in donor income and competition for resources. Significant budgetary expenditures of Ukraine are directed to defense and support of IDPs, which limits funding for social programs	Inability to fully implement projects, failure to meet the needs of the population, and reduction in the scale of programs	Coordination of efforts between organizations, creation of unified databases of needs, attraction of new donors, optimization of resource use
Lack of human resources	Lack of employees and volunteers willing to work in the dangerous conditions of the de-occupied territories due to mine danger, the risk of shelling and the need for high professional training	Slowdown in program implementation, reduced efficiency, overload of existing staff, and reduced quality of assistance	Involvement of additional volunteers, training and psychological support programs, creation of safe working conditions
Bureaucratic obstacles	Complex procedures for obtaining permits, lengthy inspections, conflicting requirements of government agencies	Delays in program implementation, loss of donor confidence, demotivation of employees, risk to the lives of victims due to delays	Simplification of administrative procedures, introduction of a “single window”, digitalization of bureaucratic processes
Insufficient coordination between organizations	Duplication of functions due to the lack of a unified database on the needs of the population and available resources	Inefficient use of resources, ignoring some of the needs of the population, and reduced program effectiveness	Unification of humanitarian programs, creation of unified databases, coordination of efforts between foundations and authorities
Psychological exhaustion of employees	Constant work in stressful and dangerous conditions, struggle with bureaucracy and limited resources lead to emotional burnout	Decreased motivation, deterioration in the quality of work, staff outflow	Organization of psychological support, staff rotation, creation of motivation and recreation programs

Source: developed by the authors.

Given this actual state of affairs, the process of finding ways to overcome these problems and optimize the activities of charitable foundations will become crucial.

Prospects for the development and support of charitable foundations in the de-occupied territories of Ukraine

The authors propose an approach to the organization of social assistance in the liberated territories that should be based on a human-centered model, and it should take into account not only the national

needs for recovery, but also the specific socio-economic circumstances of each individual. Charitable foundations working in frontline and de-occupied communities focus their programs on individual situations: providing emergency humanitarian assistance to lonely pensioners, organizing psychological support for children who have survived the occupation, providing medicines to people with chronic diseases, and helping families who have lost a breadwinner (Makedon et al., 2023).

The experience of post-industrial states, where the social policy system is based on the priority of preventive measures and comprehensive social monitoring, may be valuable for Ukraine. At the same time, the practice of charitable foundations around the world convincingly demonstrates that no model of social protection can be effective without a stable economic foundation. For Ukraine, which is forced to spend a significant share of its budget on defense, the activities of charitable organizations are becoming an important additional source of funding for social programs, as they attract funds from international donors, private companies, and civil society and direct them to meet the priority needs of people in the frontline and de-occupied areas (Makedon et al., 2025b).

For example, programs that combine material assistance tools, educational and awareness-raising activities, psychological support, and professional reintegration of internally displaced persons are already being implemented in the liberated territories (Figure 2).

FIGURE 2

Source: developed by the authors.

All measures create multidimensional support models that take into account both short-term challenges (food, shelter, medical care) and long-term tasks (restoration of infrastructure, return to normal life, formation of local communities) (Sørensen, 2024).

Social protection of the population in the de-occupied territories of Ukraine, considered in the institutional and legal dimension, should include constitutional guarantees of human rights, but their practical implementation depends on the ability of society, charitable foundations and international partners to provide comprehensive assistance in specific socio-economic conditions (Table 4) (Adegbite, 2025).

TABLE 4. Systematization of components of the development of social work of charitable foundations with the affected population in the de-occupied territories of Ukraine.

Objectives of the activity	Areas of implementation	Characteristic factors of influence: stimulating and restraining
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increasing the level of social protection of the population in the liberated communities; • preventing marginalization and overcoming poverty among the affected categories; • ensuring conditions for the full restoration of human potential and integration of IDPs; • Implementation of a human-centered approach in the practice of social work of the foundations; • creating opportunities for the realization of labor, educational and entrepreneurial potential of the population; • transformation of charitable programs into a factor of sustainable development of de-occupied communities; • social adaptation and restoration of basic services for the most vulnerable segments of the population (pensioners, children, people with disabilities); • systematic implementation of targeted and transparent assistance based on real needs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Restore the local economy through microgrants and social entrepreneurship support programs; • creation of employment funds and support for retraining of the population in cooperation with international partners; • Diversification of sources of funding for social programs from donors, businesses and communities; • introduction of active forms of support: social support, psychological assistance, educational courses; • creation of unified standards and registers of assistance recipients in communities; • strengthening the targeting of assistance through digital accounting and monitoring platforms; • rationalizing the system of humanitarian programs by coordinating the activities of several funds; • human capital development through investments in children's and youth educational initiatives. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • legalizing local businesses and encouraging their participation in social programs; • Involvement of international donors and companies in community recovery; • payment of «social rent» by business through partnership in reconstruction; • bringing social spending and support in line with European standards; • Increasing the participation of non-governmental organizations in providing assistance; • increasing transparency in the use of charitable funds; • corruption and non-transparency of decisions at the level of government agencies; • lack of awareness of the population about the programs of the foundations; • inertia of some citizens in engaging in recovery initiatives; • Risks of unpredictable social consequences in communities that have experienced the occupation.

Source: developed by the authors.

Social work in the liberated territories is in a state of constant multidirectional change, as it is influenced by both internal and external factors – from political decisions and the security situation to the activity of international donors and the level of self-organization of local communities. These processes are dynamic, as Ukraine's transitional economy, which is in the phase of deep structural transformations, is accompanied by simultaneous changes in the field of legal relations, which is manifested in the introduction of amendments and additions to the current legislation on social protection. In this context, it is necessary to realize that the social work of charitable foundations is not a static or one-dimensional activity, but rather acquires the features of proceduralism, as it is constantly adapting to new challenges, the demands of time and the needs of the population of the de-occupied regions (Shnaider, 2025). At the same time, in any given period, it is possible to record specific results of the activities of charitable institutions operating in the field of social protection, because even in the most difficult conditions, they demonstrate the ability to provide the population with a minimum level of social stability and support. Thus, at different stages of the war and recovery, authors can see how the priorities of social work have changed: from emergency humanitarian assistance in the first months to the implementation of long-term programs for psychological support, housing reconstruction, and community development in the future.

In this context, the social protection of the affected population in the de-occupied territories appears not only as a formal guarantee enshrined in national legislation, but as a result of the complex interaction of various state actors, local authorities, charitable foundations, international organizations and public initiatives, which together form a system of response and support. It characterizes the real state of the population at a particular historical moment and allows to assess the effectiveness of social assistance institutions (Zaviršek & Cox, 2024). Thus, the social activities of charitable organizations among the population affected by the liberated territories of Ukraine, is a complex multi-level system that combines the assimilation of international experience with the development of its own innovative approaches to address specific problems caused by the hostilities and reconstruction processes. It is through this complex interaction of various factors that an effective mechanism of social protection for residents who survived the occupation is formed and determines the ability of Ukrainian society to ensure stable development even in the most difficult conditions.

DISCUSSION

Comparison of the obtained scientific results with existing publications demonstrates their compliance with previous research in the field of charitable activities, but at the same time reveals a number of unexplored aspects that require additional scientific study. In particular, the results confirm the views of Sycheva and Polonets (2020) on the evolution from one-time humanitarian measures to systemic social activities, but our study for the first time highlights the peculiarities of the regions liberated from occupation, where the volume of destruction and social challenges require innovative methods of work. Similarities can also be observed with the views of Kharabet et al. (2017), who emphasized the need to modernize the social support system, but our findings complement this view by analyzing administrative obstacles and the lack of qualified personnel, which directly affects the performance of charitable foundations in the liberated communities.

There is also a correspondence with the work of Nilsson et al. (2020), who emphasized the role of ethical principles in the development of philanthropy, as the results of our analysis show that volunteer activities in dangerous conditions are based on moral motives. At the same time, the data obtained showed that this factor is not enough in the liberated territories, as psychological overload and serious security threats require additional institutional means of supporting employees and volunteers. The results also correlate with the findings of Pankova and Kasperovych (2022), who considered volunteerism as a resource for the restoration of the state, but our study shows that in the case of the liberated territories, without proper coordination between organizations and the authorities, there is a duplication of tasks, which reduces the effectiveness of social initiatives. In the global context, the results partially coincide with Erdilmen (2025), who examined the aspects of localization of humanitarian activities, but in the Ukrainian context, the work of foundations is not only focused on providing humanitarian aid, but also performs the functions of restoring infrastructure and creating the foundations for local development. Similar parallels can be drawn with the findings of Završek and Cox (2024), who studied social work in armed conflicts, but in the Ukrainian context, charitable institutions also play a role of compensation for state institutions in the field of basic social services.

The scientific novelty of the study lies in the identification of a human-centered model of social work of charitable organizations that takes into account not only the typical needs of the affected population, but also the specific features of the liberated territories, characterized by the destruction of infrastructure, a high degree of trauma and a difficult security situation.

CONCLUSIONS

The analysis of the problems and challenges related to social initiatives of charitable foundations in the de-occupied territories of Ukraine shows a significant increase in the role of civil society in providing social protection and restoration of the affected communities. It was determined that charitable activities used to be sporadic, but after the outbreak of full-scale war, they turned into a stable support institution that covers a wide range of needs, from humanitarian aid to psychological, educational and legal rehabilitation.

Charitable foundations in the liberated territories are not only providers of material assistance, but also catalysts for social change. Through a combination of humanitarian and reintegration programs, they contribute to restoring infrastructure, improving legal security, and developing human capital. However, their work is hampered by the destruction of infrastructure, security risks, and bureaucratic barriers. Nevertheless, charitable organizations demonstrate significantly higher responsiveness than government agencies, which points to the need for deeper coordination between the state, communities, and foundations to improve the effectiveness of social support.

It has been proven that the future development of charitable foundations is associated with the transition to a human-centered model of assistance focused on individual needs, from targeted support for pensioners to specialized rehabilitation programs for children and women who have experienced war trauma. The introduction of digital technologies is promising: maintaining registers of needs, online consultations, and electronic logistics.

These measures will increase the level of transparency, accuracy and trust in the funds, and create the basis for a new system of social work that combines rapid response with long-term recovery.

The study showed that the future of social work in the liberated territories will depend on the ability to combine international experience with Ukrainian innovative practices. The integration of global approaches through prevention, psychological support, and human capacity development with local community mobilization will be the basis for an effective support system. A key factor is financial sustainability, which will be ensured by diversifying funding, attracting business, international partners and local resources. In such a transformation, charitable foundations go beyond humanitarian aid, becoming an effective tool for rebuilding trust and sustainable development of communities that have survived the occupation.

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